

The Great Mughal and the Orlov: One and the Same Diamond?

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One of the most famous stones mentioned in the gemmological literature is the so-called Great Mughal diamond, described and depicted in a 17th-century work of Jean-Baptiste Tavernier. According to Tavernier, this specimen weighed ~286 metric carats (upon recalculation from Eastern units); it was not mentioned in later sources referring to the Mughal court. In the 18th century, however, a diamond reminiscent of the Great Mughal appeared on the market—it is known today as the Orlov (189.62 ct). Some researchers have suggested that these specimens could be identical, if not for the fact that the Orlov weighs about 90 ct less than the stone reported by Tavernier. This discrepancy may be explained by the inference that Tavernier never actually examined the stone, but he only described it from accounts given by others. This deduction, together with new evidence showing that the stone actually weighed ~193.5 ct, indicates a high likelihood that the Great Mughal is the same as the Orlov diamond.

The Journal of Gemmology, **35**(1), 2016, pp. 56–63, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15506/JoG.2016.35.1.56>
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Introduction

In the work of Jean-Baptiste Tavernier (1605–1689), French diamantaire and traveller to India and other exotic locales (Figure 1), there is a description of one of the largest diamonds in the collection of the Mughal emperor Aurangzeb (reigned 1658–1707)—a specimen weighing ~286 ct known as the Great Mughal (or Great Mogul). Most who have written on the history of this diamond do not question the credibility of Tavernier's account (King, 1867; Jagnaux, 1885; Shipley, 1955; Bruton, 1970; Moneta Cavenago-Bignami, 1980; Harlow, 1998; Balfour, 2009). The Frenchman's information regarding this stone is examined further in this article, and its possible relation to the Orlov diamond is explored.

Background

One of the most frequently cited historical European travel writers is Jean-Baptiste Tavernier. This privately active gem merchant made six journeys to the East during the period 1630–1668, visiting among other countries Turkey, Persia and India (e.g. Figure 2). In this last region—the first known source of diamonds—Tavernier was most interested in just these stones, which was reflected in the work he published in 1676, wherein he described the methods used to mine them and problems connected with their trade.

Even though the Frenchman's reports pertaining to these issues are not the only ones from this period, his writings also contain an account of unique value regarding the gems

Figure 1: Jean-Baptiste Tavernier is shown wearing an Oriental costume in this portrait by Nicolas de Largillière. The painting currently resides at Herzog Anton Ulrich Museum, Braunschweig, Germany.

of Aurangzeb, the ruler of the Mughal Empire (Howard, 1677; Master, 1911; Moreland, 1931; de Coutre, 1991). Aurangzeb's valuables were shown to Tavernier by the imperial gem keeper, Akel Khan. Most of these were not especially notable by Mughal standards, as they 'only' weighed from several carats to about 60 ct. However, according to Tavernier (1692), there was one exceptional stone (as quoted in and translated by Streeter, 1882, pp. 69–70; see also Balfour, 2009):

The first piece that Akel Khan placed in my hands was the great diamond, which is rose cut, round and very high on one side. On the lower edge there is a slight crack, and a little flaw in it. Its water is fine, and weighs $319\frac{1}{2}$ ratis [*sic*], which makes 280 of our carats, the rati being $\frac{7}{8}$ of a carat.

Tavernier, who included a drawing of this gem in his account (Figure 3), claimed that the keeper allowed him to personally examine and weigh

Figure 2: Tavernier's travels to the East were recorded in various manuscripts, such as this one from 1692.

the diamond. He also reported that the original rough stone weighed about 790 carats, and in 1656 it was given as a gift to Aurangzeb's father Emperor Shah Jahan (reigned 1628–1658; Figure 4) by Mir Jumla, previously a dignitary in the court at Golconda, in recognition of his support of the Mughals. The stone was most probably pilfered from one of the temples in Karnataka, India, by soldiers of Mir Jumla during military operations conducted there in 1642–1652 (Gemelli Careri, 1700). The diamond was reportedly cut by a Venetian, Hortensio Borgio, who worked in India

Figure 3: Tavernier's drawing of the Great Mughal diamond appeared in his 1692 monograph.

Figure 4: Emperor Shah Jahan is shown on a throne, flanked on the left by his three eldest sons—Dara Shikoh, Shah Shuja and Aurangzeb—while their maternal grandfather, Asaf Khan, stands to the right. The painting dates from the Mughal Period, circa AD 1628. Source: Aga Khan Museum, www.agakhanmuseum.org/collection/artifact/shah-jahan-his-three-sons-and-asaf-khan-akm124.

during the second part of the 17th century. The reported weight of the resulting stone, 319½ rattis—indicated by Tavernier (1692) as being

Figure 5: The 189.62 ct Orlov diamond is shown here in the Imperial Sceptre, part of the Diamond Fund collection of the Moscow Kremlin. Photo © Elkan Wijnberg.

equivalent to 280 ‘of our carats’—probably is equal to ~286 metric carats (see below).

The diamond described by Tavernier has not been mentioned in later sources referring to the Mughal period.

Correlations with the Orlov Diamond

The stone from Tavernier’s drawing and description has been noted as being similar to the Mughal-cut Orlov diamond (Figures 5 and 6), which weighs 189.62 ct and is presently kept at the Moscow Kremlin in Russia (Rybakov, 1975; Polynina, 2012; Malecka, 2014b; Shcherbina, 2014). Several legends circulate about the origins of the Orlov diamond. The most popular of them, which can be dated to Europe in the late 18th century, states this gem was taken by a French soldier from an Indian temple in Srirangam in present-day Tamil Nadu State (Dutens, 1783). Another rumour indicated that this stone was to have been an ornament for the throne of Nadir Shah, ruler of Persia, who in 1739 plundered the Mughal treasury (Pallas, 1805; Fersman 1924–25). However, according to documents from Russian archives, during the rule of Nadir Shah (1736–1747), the Orlov was in fact the property of the Persians (although it was not necessarily kept in Persia). We do know for certain that it was taken from the Persian city of Isfahan to Amsterdam by an Armenian merchant. In Amsterdam, it was sold to Catherine II, the empress of Russia (Malecka, 2014b; Malecka, in prep.-b).

Both the Great Mughal and Orlov diamonds have the same type of cut. According to Balfour (2009), “the pattern of facets is not dissimilar” and, even more importantly, there is a small indentation in the Orlov that corresponds to the small crack on the stone described by Tavernier. Even though the similarity of these gems was already noticed in the 19th century by European writers, they were restrained from equating the stones by the information on the weight of the Great Mughal diamond as given by Tavernier. Some writers justified the differences in weight by pointing out Tavernier’s probable mistake when weighing Aurangzeb’s stone, or that this specimen decreased in size (i.e. through recutting) at a later time (Anonymous, 1853; Schrauf, 1869; Ball, 1889; Fersman, 1922; Fersman 1924–25).

However, Aziz (1942) reported that some Mughal authors pointed to a different weight for this stone than that given by Tavernier (see page 60). He did not correlate the identity of this gem with the Orlov diamond, perhaps because the weight of the Orlov was usually given by older authorities as 185 Amsterdam or Russian carats, whereas Aziz described it as weighing 194.75 ct, similar to that given by some 19th century Russian sources (Anonymous, 1866; Aziz, 1942; Kuznetsova, 2009; Zimin and Sokolov, 2013).

Present Research

Previous writers pondering the correlation between the Great Mughal and Orlov diamonds did not analyse court texts from the Mughal Empire in the Persian language or sources available in the Russian language. The present author's research has been largely based on such material.

A matter of key significance is to determine the Western weight conversions that Tavernier used for the Indian units of the Great Mughal—*rattis*, also known as *surkhs* (Halhed, 1776). Weight units for gems (as weights and measures in general) were quite varied in Asia, Africa and Europe depending on the epoch and geographical location. Normally, the Eastern authors did not specify the local units for the weights of gems they were describing. The weight of identically named units could also differ in reference to gems vs. metals (Lockyer, 1711; Kelly, 1832; Hinz, 1955).

When describing Aurangzeb's diamond, Tavernier's weight conversion was that 1 ratti corresponded to 0.875 of 'our carats' (Tavernier, 1692). Valentine Ball (1889) maintained that the Frenchman converted Eastern weight units for gems into Florentine carats, which were equivalent to about 0.196 g. Ball based his argument on information contained in Tavernier's work pertaining to a diamond weighing 139.5 Florentine carats—the largest diamond in Europe at that time—seen by him in the collection of the Great Prince of Tuscany and known later as the Florentine diamond. The weight of this stone, cited by Tavernier and lost since the times of World War I, was very close to the 137.27 metric carats of The Great Diamond of Tuscany, as it is known from later sources (Ball, 1889; Balfour, 2009).

In fact, it is probable that the weight of the Florentine diamond was reported by Tavernier in

local (Florentine) units, as he did sometimes in the case of gems that he saw or heard about during his Eastern voyages (see below; Tavernier, 1692). The present author did not, however, find any information suggesting that the Florentine carat was used universally by Western gem traders at that time. Therefore, one may wonder if this conversion was applied by Tavernier consistently in reference to the various gems mentioned by him. In this author's view, it is more probable that in writing

Figure 6: Various views of the Orlov diamond are shown in this 1767 drawing that was made in Amsterdam by Frans de Bakker. If the Orlov was in fact the same as the Great Mughal diamond, then the image of the rough stone in the upper left must have been conjectural, since the diamond was previously cut in the 17th century. Source: Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, www.rijksmuseum.nl/nl/collectie/RP-P-1911-2912.

‘our carats’—similarly as for French livres, which he described as ‘our money’—the famous diamantaire had in mind the French carat commonly used in his home country, the weight of which was about 0.205 g (Tavernier, 1692). In that case, 1 ratti would correspond to about 0.179 g or about 0.896 metric carats, and the 319.5 rattis reported for the Great Mughal Diamond would thus correspond to ~286 ct.

However, according to 17th century Mughal and Deccani chronicles, and most importantly a letter from Shah Jahan (the owner of the stone) to the king of Golconda, the weight of the Great Mughal diamond was 9 *tanks*, which some of these sources indicate is equivalent to 216 rattis or surkhs (e.g. Mīr ʿĀlam, AH¹ 1266; Khāfi Khān, 1869; Kanbūh and Yazdani, 1939; Aziz, 1942; Sarkar, 1951; Awranghābādī et al., 1999), rather than the 319.5 rattis reported by Tavernier. A weight of 216 rattis corresponds to ~193.5 ct, if the metric carat conversion suggested above is used. Again, the current weight of the Orlov diamond is 189.62 ct.

Tavernier and the Great Mughal Diamond

If in fact the Great Mughal was actually somewhat over 190 ct, why did Tavernier overstate the weight? For this we are left with conjectures. To the best of this author’s knowledge, there are three possible explanations: (1) a mistake in estimating its weight, (2) purposeful deceit or (3) his knowledge of the diamond was gained indirectly, for example, on the basis of accounts given by others.

The possibility that Tavernier made a mistake in estimating the weight of the diamond by nearly 90 ct seems impossible for such an experienced diamantaire (Paxton, 1856). Therefore one might consider that Tavernier deliberately overstated the weight of the diamond, perhaps intending to evoke a stronger impression on those readers who were told since the 16th century about the fabulous riches of the Mughal Empire (Foster, 1921; Keene and Kaoukji, 2001). However, this author feels that the most probable explanation is that Tavernier possessed only indirect knowledge of the Great Mughal diamond. It is known that the Frenchman did in fact include in his work drawings and detailed descriptions of gems that he did not examine personally. Among this group

were, for example, gems of the ruler of Bijapur and the Shah of Persia; he most probably gained the information about these during his travels from royal gem keepers or merchants.² It is also probable that he obtained knowledge about one of the most famous diamonds of the Muslim world—the Great Table, from which were cut the Nur al-Ayn and Darya-ye Nur stones now found in the treasury of Iran—not by analysing the original gem, as he claims, but by examining a model of the stone (Malecka, 2014a; Malecka, in prep.-a).

The possibility that Tavernier gained information about the Great Mughal diamond from third parties is supported by his drawing of this stone (again, see Figure 3), which was described by one 19th century scholar as ‘rough’ or ‘rude’ (Maskelyne, 1860a,b). His drawing could easily have been made on the basis of a description, and therefore not all the details depicted in it should be assumed credible.³ Indirect knowledge may account for the fact that depictions of other historical diamonds may differ significantly from one another (ʿIṭimād al-Salṭānah, AH 1349; Tavakkulī Bazzāz, AH 1380; Diba et al., 1998; Raby, 1999).

If indeed Tavernier obtained information indirectly about the Great Mughal diamond, this certainly does not preclude that the presentation of Aurangzeb’s jewels, which he mentioned, actually took place. The showing of valuables from the treasury was often practised in the Muslim world (al-Tanūkhī, AH 1393). It should be underscored, however, that during Tavernier’s visit, the most valuable jewels of the Mughal court were not in the possession of Aurangzeb, but rather were kept by his jailed father Shah Jahan, who refused to give them up despite requests from his son (Manucci, 1907; Begley and Desai, 1990). As a connoisseur of gems, Shah Jahan most certainly was attached to his collection of precious objects. It should be emphasized as well that in the Islamic world, the

² Another potential source of Tavernier’s information—court inventories—should be excluded, in this author’s opinion. First, there is no evidence that the Frenchman had any access to them. Second, a survey of equivalent surviving material from the Islamic world shows that the weight and/or drawings of even large stones was never or rarely noted (Topkapı Sarayı Müzesi Arşivi, AH 1091).

³ It has also been suggested that the drawings contained in Tavernier’s work of the stones he most certainly saw and handled may not be fully credible (Sucher, 2009).

¹ In reporting the year of ancient scripts, ‘AH’ means *Anno Hegirae*, or ‘in the year of the Hijra’.

involuntary transfer of valuable stones to another ruler indicated the giver's subservient status; this was particularly the case for diamonds in Mughal India, as their possession was an imperial monopoly (Ferishta, 1829; de Coultre, 1991; Boym, 2009; Malecka, in prep.-b).

It is well worth adding that the most important gems, functioning as regalia, were often worn by the rulers personally. It is also known that Shah Jahan would display a diamond given to him by Mir Jumla by placing it on his turban (Valentijn, 1726; Malecka, in prep.-b). This author finds it doubtful that Shah Jahan would have given a stone of this importance to his son prior to being incarcerated. Such an event would have undoubtedly been noted by court chroniclers scrupulously registering movements of large gems. In view of the above considerations, this author suspects, as did some 19th–20th century authorities, that during Tavernier's visit to the Mughal court, the Great Mughal diamond in fact was in the possession of Shah Jahan, and this excluded the possibility of it being examined by the Frenchman (Maskelyne, 1860a; Aziz, 1942).

Due to large discrepancies regarding the weight of the diamond from Persian-language sources of the epoch as compared to Tavernier's work, the present author deduces that Tavernier did not actually see the Great Mughal diamond. The presumed weight of the Great Mughal, however, both before (~790 ct) and after fashioning (~286 ct), probably was not invented by the Frenchman himself.⁴ Tavernier reported the mass of imperial gems by using various units popular in India, which he recalculated into carats only in the case of the diamond in question. It may therefore be supposed that the presumed weights of the Great Mughal both prior to and after polishing were obtained from the imperial treasure keeper, who could have demonstrated the tendency—not at all alien to his profession—to overstate the weight of gems possessed by his master (Brydges Jones, 1833; Meen and Tushingam, 1968; Malecka,

in prep.-b). Most likely, this same source also provided Tavernier with information pertaining to the polished stone's appearance.

Conclusions

According to Persian-language sources from the epoch, in 1656 the Great Mughal diamond weighed about 193.5 ct. This is quite close to the 189.62 ct of the Orlov diamond at the Kremlin. The weight difference of ~3.8 ct is very small compared to the sizes of these stones. In fact, various sources from the Great Mughal's time period and cultural circle have indicated that the weight of an important gem could differ by more than a dozen carats (Sāravī Fath' Allāh, AH 1371; Sālūr et al., AH 1374; Riḍā' Qulī Khān Hidāyat, AH 1380; Fasā'ī Ḥusainī and Fasā'ī Rastgār, 1988). In this author's opinion, due to similarities in weight, shape, type of cut and flaws, the stone given in 1656 by Mir Jumla to Shah Jahan was in fact the same as the diamond presently known as the Orlov. Since it must have been presented to Shah Jahan in polished form, the abovementioned account by Tavernier about it being cut by Hortensio Borgio cannot be true.

This article provides strong evidence that Tavernier did not see the diamond he described, since during his visit at the Mughal court the stone most probably was in the possession of Shah Jahan. The scene of examination of this stone was then contrived by the Frenchman in order to make the text more attractive and was incorporated into the chapter containing descriptions of Aurangzeb's valuables shown to him.

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⁴ According to eminent Russian mineralogist Alexander Fersman, one of the few experts who has studied the Orlov, this stone was cut probably from a rough stone weighing ~400 ct (Fersman, 1955). Assuming that the Great Mughal diamond is identical to the Orlov, this provides an additional argument for negating Tavernier's statement that the rough stone from which the Great Mughal was cut weighed ~790 ct.

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Acknowledgement

The author wishes to thank three anonymous reviewers for their useful comments and assistance in the preparation of this paper.